

Management Strategies Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State

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Abstract

The study investigated management strategies adopted by head teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions were formulated to guide the study and three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey design was adopted. From a population of 6,648 primary school teachers and 1068 head teachers, a sample of 1050 teachers and 525 head teachers was drawn using simple random sampling technique. A 23 item instrument titled “Strategies for Quality Assurance Questionnaire (SQAQ)” was used for data collection. The instrument was structured on a 4 rating scale of strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighed 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively. The validation of the instrument was established by three experts, two from Department of Educational Management and Policy and one from the department of Educational Foundation, Faculty of Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, while Cronbach’s alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument which yielded the overall coefficient value of 0.89, 0.78 and 0.74 for the three components of the instrument. Data obtained were analyzed using mean and t-test. The findings of the study indicated among others that head teachers adopt professional development training, school facility management, effective instructional supervision strategies for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra state. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that the government should provide clear and comprehensive quality assurance for primary schools, outlining specific standards and expectations. They should also ensure adequate allocation of resources, including teaching materials, technology, and personnel, to support effective teaching and learning.

Key Words: Management, Management strategies, Head teachers, Quality Assurance

Introduction

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Education is viewed as an instrument for national development and social change since a nation is as good as the kind of education system it operates. In Nigeria, education has been regarded as the single most important industry for the production of high level manpower and human capital of the entire society. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) in her National Policy on Education remarked that education in Nigeria is an instrument par excellence for effective national development. The Nigeria's National Policy on Education further stated that Nigerian education is aimed at providing education that is qualitative, comprehensive, functional and relevant to the needs of the society. This calls for quality education at all levels in the country to meet the aspirations of individuals and the society, especially in this era of knowledge-driven society and global competitiveness. Presently Nigeria operates a 9-3-4 system of education with the three sub-sectors namely; (1) basic education; (2) post basic education and career development; (3) tertiary education. The focus of this study is on the basic education which is made up of pre-primary and primary education but specifically on primary education.

Primary education is the foundation of the child's education which forms an integral part of his or her early education that may be formal or informal. This type of education is given in an educational institution to children aged 6 to 11 (Ezeagu, 2019). This educational level of the child provides all round development for the child, for example physical, motor, health, nutritional, intellectual, aesthetic, emotional and social development. The development of children at this level is important because whatever is learnt at this stage is transferred to future learning. Primary education is seen by parents and society as a necessity because of the demands of the society. This calls for quality in the management of primary education.

Quality has been variously described as a measure for excellence, quality as perfection, quality as value for money, quality as customer satisfaction, quality as fitness for purpose and quality as transformation. Adebayo, Oyenike and Adesoji (2014) enumerated two aspects of quality in education which are both internal and external. The internal aspect they stated is the implementation of the national objectives which are pre-requisite to the achievement of quality in educational institutions. Ajayi and Akindutire (2017) described quality as the totality of the performance of a process, product or service in customer or clients' perception. Fadokun (2015) explained that quality education is the efficiency of an educational provision in meeting its goals as well as its relevance to human and societal conditions. It is important to note that for any nation to rise to a standard worthy enough for her to compete globally in the leagues of Nations, such a nation must ensure that high quality is attained and sustained in her educational system. The extent to which the above expectation is achieved depends largely on the quality of education offered to the citizenry. The quality of education is the prime factor that determines the worth and or significance of the system to both the recipients and the society at large. Quality assurance in Nigeria education system is an agenda that gives educators serious concern about the system.

Quality assurance in education consists all proactive measures adopted by a country to ensure that the system standard remain high enough to produce results set for it. Thus, quality standard in education is the benchmark that should guide the performance of the education system.

Quality assurance in education is in fact a process of monitoring standard of output of the education system through inspection. It is in fact a process of continuous improvement in the quality of teaching and learning activities. Thus, quality assurance in primary schools is operationally defined in this study as all the activities or roles performed by head-teachers in order to ensure that education provided in primary schools are of high academic standard and meets the needs and aspirations of stakeholders. A head-teacher is the most senior teacher within a school. He/she is responsible for managing the school and making sure that everything is smoothly on a day –to – day basis. He/she provides guidance and expertise and he is also the most influential presence within the school community. Ultimately he/she is held responsible for the overall education and academic achievements of the school. It is the responsibility of the head teacher to create a productive learning environment for staff and pupils.

The objectives of quality assurance in basic education as outlined by Federal Ministry of Education (2014) are as follows: (1) ensure that quality teaching and learning take place in schools and centres; (2) create a valid and reliable database that can support or inform policies and decisions aimed at improving the overall effectiveness of school and centres; (3) monitor the level of learning achievement as well as other educational performance indicators in schools and centres; (4) set minimum uniform standard nationwide; (5) ascertain that the approved curriculum is operational in schools and centres and that stated objectives are being achieved; (6) provide regular report on the state of education in Nigeria; (7) advise on the provision of proper and adequate physical facilities in educational institutions; (8) provide professional support to teachers in the area of pedagogy and classroom management as well as to school administrators in the area of school management. These objectives suggest that quality assurance is a sine-qua-non in the educational system if high academic standard must be attained.

The Federal Ministry of Education (2010) outlined strategies for achieving quality assurance as follows: (1) effective evaluation of students' learning outcomes (2) adequate provision of qualified teachers and their professional development; (3) enrichment of curriculum to the needs and aspiration of the learner; (4) development of incentive structures to attract, motivate and retain high quality teachers; (5) adequate care, guidance and support of the learners; (6) quality leadership and management; (7) management of school facilities; (8) periodic instructional supervision; (9) use of recommended instructional methods; (10) use of instructional materials. For the purpose of this study, the following strategies will be examined: (i) professional development training; (ii) management of school facilities; and (iii) periodic instructional supervision. These strategies are considered because of the peculiarities of level of education involved.

Professional development training is one major strategies employed by head-teachers of public primary schools for implementing quality assurance guidelines. Professional development programmes are committed to improving the teachers' functions and growing their skills. It is through professional development that schools realize multiple goals, ranging from training teachers in the use the latest technology, to help them grow their skills in implementing

pedagogical best functions and even aiding teachers as they innovate in pursuit of improved educational outcome.

Management of school facilities form another strategy employed by head-teachers for implementing quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools. King'oina (2014) posited that for efficient educational management, facilities are needed to help the school to determine the number of pupils to be accommodated, number of teachers and non-teaching personnel to be employed and the cost determination for the efficient management of the system. Olutola (2015) contends that the school environment affects academic achievement of pupils. Facilities such as school buildings, desks, seats, chalkboard, teaching aids, and cupboard are ingredients for effective teaching and learning. Onyango (2016) portends that facilities should be regularly and frequently inspected or checked for any possible hazards. Any hazards to the students' health or safety should be eliminated immediately. Resources especially buildings and facilities are of considerable investment of public funds and maintenance is essential to protect this investment.

Another important strategy which could be employed by head-teachers in implementing quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools is periodic instructional supervision. Baffour-Awuah (2017) opined that instructional supervision deals with monitoring teachers' instruction-related duties, providing teachers with teaching resource, visiting classrooms to observe lessons, and providing assistance and support to help teachers do their work effectively. The use of recommended instructional methods is another strategy employed by head-teachers for implementing quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools. Reilly (2015) emphasized pedagogical premises that must be taken into consideration in the choice of instructional methods in secondary schools which include that; (i) learners have distinctive perspectives or frames of reference contributed to by their history, environment, interests and goals, beliefs and ways of thinking; (ii) learners have unique differences, including emotional state of mind, learning rates, learning styles, stages of development, abilities, talents and feelings of efficacy. Okobia (2018) emphasized that the adoption of instructional strategies that take into consideration learners' background, unique differences and interests, interpersonal relationship and their natural desire to explore their surroundings and acquire new knowledge. It is within this milieu that learning becomes meaningful, integrative, value-based, challenging and exciting.

It is important to note that successful application of quality assurance strategies spells out proper implementation of quality assurance guidelines. It is however unfortunate that some of these strategies seem not to be applied by head teachers. The decline in quality is brought about by a number of factors, which include demography, poor state of the economy, weak internal capacity, poor governance, poor research activities, brain drain, political interference, incessant industrial actions, unruly and destructive conduct of undergraduates, poor preparation of entering students, unsuitable policy environment, poor funding, shortage of instructional materials, laboratory equipment and poor library facilities; other factors are unexpected consequences of government policy at the primary levels, all of which have had devastating effect on the quality of education (Ijeoma and Osagie, 2015; Uvah, 2015). It is unfortunate that some of the public primary

schools in Anambra state do not study in a conducive environment, some do not have learning materials and some teachers do not go for professional training to improve on their knowledge. It is against this background that this study was undertaken.

Statement of the Problem

In recent years, the Nigerian primary education sector has witnessed numerous challenges that have adversely affected the quality of teaching and learning. As the foundational level of the educational system, the state of public primary schools is critical to national development. However, in Anambra State, many public primary schools are characterized by inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teaching and learning materials, poor supervision, ill-equipped libraries and laboratories, low teacher morale, frequent policy shifts, and inadequate funding. These issues collectively point to systemic weaknesses that undermine the effectiveness and quality of primary education in the state.

Despite the strategic role head-teachers are expected to play in managing schools and ensuring quality assurance, there appears to be a gap in the actual management practices employed to address these challenges. The persistence of these problems suggests that either effective strategies are not being adopted or that the existing ones are insufficient in addressing the quality concerns in public primary schools. This situation is worrisome because the quality of education at the primary level serves as the bedrock for subsequent educational achievement. If not urgently addressed, the continuous deterioration of standards at this level could have long-term consequences on the entire educational system, leading to poor student performance, low literacy rates, and ultimately, a poorly educated workforce.

It is against this backdrop that this study seeks to investigate the management strategies adopted by head-teachers for ensuring quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine management strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the study investigated:

1. Professional development training strategy adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State.
2. School facility management strategy adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State.
3. Effective instructional supervision strategy adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State.

Research Questions

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The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are professional development training strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State?
2. What are school facility management strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State?
3. What are effective instructional supervision strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on professional development training strategies adopted by head- teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on school facility management strategies adopted by head – teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers on effective instructional supervision strategies adopted by head- teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.

Methods

A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study which was carried out in public primary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Three research questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. From a population of 6,648 primary school teachers and 1068 head teachers, a sample of 1050 teachers and 525 head teachers was drawn using simple random sampling technique. A researchers' developed instrument titled "Strategies Adopted for Quality Assurance Questionnaire" (SAQAQ) which was validated by three experts was used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach's Alpha and this yielded reliability coefficients 0.89, 0.78 and 0.74 for the three components of the instrument. The instrument was considered reliable in line with Nworgu (2015), who stated that if the co-efficient obtained for an instrument is up to 0.70 and above, the instrument should be considered good enough to be used for a study. The direct administration and retrieval method was used for data collection. A total of 1575 copies of the questionnaire were administered while 1512 were retrieved and used for data analysis. Mean was used to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test all the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. For the research questions, a mean rating of 2.50 and above was interpreted as agree while mean rating of less than 2.50 was interpreted as

disagree. The null hypothesis was rejected where the p-value associated with the t-cal was less than 0.05 whereas the null hypothesis was not rejected where the p-value was greater than 0.05.

Results

Table 1: Mean Ratings on Professional Development Training Strategies Adopted By Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Organize seminars on publications on current trends in the field supporting teachers for research	680	586	204	42	2.78	.87	Agree
2.	Insist on teachers' membership of professional association like TRCN as requirement for practice	564	619	298	31	2.90	.81	Agree
3.	Assess research in business education to ensure quality	560	682	243	27	2.93	.80	Agree
4.	Establish and ensure functional entrepreneurship development education (EDE) for quality in the programme	532	744	226	10	2.82	.90	Agree
5.	Sponsor teachers to workshops and conferences regularly	444	734	309	25	2.97	.79	Agree
6.	Sponsor teachers for short courses on the use of e- learning technologies for teaching and learning effectiveness regularly	346	797	310	59	2.89	.80	Agree
7.	Host lectures and make teachers' attendance mandatory	383	799	288	42	2.75	.86	Agree
8.	Organize leadership development programmes regularly	307	821	336	48	2.88	.80	Agree

The analysis in Table 1 shows that the respondents agreed with all the eight items as professional development training strategies adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State. The mean ratings for the eight items ranged from 2.75 to 2.93. The standard deviation scores which ranged from .79 to .90 showed that the respondents were more agreeing in their ratings of item 5 (SD=.79) and more disagreeing with item 9 as indicated by its large standard deviation of .90.

Table 2: Mean Ratings on School Facility Management Strategies Adopted by Head-Teachers for quality assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State.

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Ensure adequacy of infrastructural facilities	329	720	398	65	2.51	.96	Agree
2.	Check internet connection to classrooms	365	768	347	32	2.48	.78	Disagree

3. Ensure adequacy and properly ventilation of classrooms for effective teaching and learning	463	663	345	41	2.64	.89	Agree
4. Monitor school website for effective use	530	670	287	25	2.75	.83	Agree
5. Check laboratory equipment and materials for adequacy and currency regularly	639	602	209	62	2.82	.84	Agree
6. Check materials in the electronic libraries for adequacy and currency regularly	547	683	212	70	2.74	.82	Agree
7. Ensure use of updated textbooks and journals for currency and comprehensiveness	453	758	248	53	2.92	.86	Agree
8. Ensure adequate provisions for ICT utilization by teachers for instructional delivery	406	785	307	14	2.82	.84	Agree
9. Check and ensure provision for regular power supply to offices, classrooms and laboratories	419	773	312	8	2.85	.83	Agree

Table 2 shows the mean ratings of school facility management strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance. The respondents agreed to all the nine items as being adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State with their mean ranging from 2.51 to 2.92. The standard deviation scores showed that the respondents were more agreeing in their mean ratings of item 10 ($SD=.78$) and more disagreeing with item 9 as indicated by its large standard deviation of .96.

Table 3: Mean Ratings on Effective Instructional Supervision Strategies Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State?

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	I constantly review contents taught in my school	376	848	239	49	3.03	.73	Agree
2.	Ensure that question papers are moderated before they are administered	384	851	234	43	3.04	.72	Agree
3.	Ensure that appropriate methods are employed by teachers in my school	422	769	290	31	3.05	.74	Agree
4.	I constantly evaluate instructional materials used by teachers in my school to ensure suitability	417	734	308	53	3.00	.79	Agree
5.	Monitor students during practical exercises in my school	435	612	387	78	2.93	.86	Agree
6.	Ensure high level of discipline during classroom instruction in my school	321	719	443	29	2.88	.75	Agree

As shown in Table 3, the respondents agreed to the six items as effective instructional supervision strategies adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State. The mean rating for the six items ranged from 2.88 to 3.05. The standard deviation scores

showed that the respondents were more agreeing in their mean ratings of item 2 ($SD=.72$) and more disagreeing with item 5 as indicated by its large standard deviation of .86.

Table 4: t-test Comparison of Mean Scores of Head-teachers And Teachers on the Professional Development Training Strategies Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Head-teachers	496	3.12	.52	1510	4.25	.000	Sig
Teachers	1016	3.00	.46				

Table 4 shows that the mean score for head-teachers ($M=3.12, SD=.52$) was significantly greater than that of teachers ($M=3.00, SD=.42$); $t (1510) 4.25, p=.000$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on the professional development training strategies employed by head-teachers in the implementation of quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools in Anambra State was therefore rejected.

Table 5: t-test comparison of mean scores of head-teachers and teachers on school facility management strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Head-teachers	496	3.07	.52	1510	2.05	.041	Sig
Teachers	1016	3.01	.42				

Table 5 shows that the mean score for head-teachers ($M=3.07, SD=.52$) was significantly greater than that of teachers ($M=3.01, SD=.42$) $t (1510) 2.05, p=.000$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on the school facility management strategies employed by head-teachers in the implementation of quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools in Anambra State was therefore rejected.

Table 6: t-test comparison of mean scores of head-teachers and teachers on effective instructional supervision strategies adopted by head-teachers for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State.

Source of variation	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	P-value	Decision
Head-teachers	496	3.04	.54	1510	6.23	.000	Sig
Teachers	1016	2.86	.51				

Table 6 shows that the mean score for head-teachers ($M=3.04$, $SD=.54$) was significantly greater than that of teachers ($M=2.86$, $SD=.51$); $t(1510) 6.23$, $p=.000$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on effective instructional supervision strategies employed by head-teachers in the implementation of quality assurance guidelines in public primary schools in Anambra State was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Results

Professional Development Programmes as a Strategy Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary School in Anambra State.

The analysis in Table 1 indicated that the respondents agreed that professional development programmes are adopted by head-teachers of public primary schools for quality assurance in Anambra State. The analysis in Table 6 also showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of head-teachers and teachers on adoption of professional development programmes as a strategy for quality assurance by head-teachers of public primary schools in Anambra State. Therefore, the two results show that head-teachers and teachers in Anambra State, irrespective of their position agreed that head-teachers of public primary schools in the state adopt professional development programmes for quality assurance. The idea behind the adoption of professional development programmes for quality assurance is that head-teachers in the state organize seminars on publications on current trends in the field to support teachers for research; insist on teachers membership of professional association like TRCN as requirement for practice; assess research in business education to ensure quality; and establish and ensure functional entrepreneurship development education (EDE) for quality in the programme. The respondents also agreed that primary school head-teachers schools. Certainly, the adoption of professional development programmes suggests that the head-teachers acknowledged the influence of staff training on improving teaching and learning process and the overall quality in primary schools and the need to prioritize that when establishing new schools. They are cognizant of their position as instructional leaders and as such the onus is on them to ensure that professional development programmes are organized for the teachers regularly to ensure they employ the most appropriate pedagogic practices.

The results above are in agreement with the results of an earlier study by Arogundade and Belo (2019) that carried out a study on quality assurance and internal efficiency of primary school

teachers in Ekiti State. Their study revealed that primary school head-teachers in Ekiti State encourages their staff to participate in professional development programmes such as workshops, seminars and conference in order to improve their skills. The study also found that there was no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female teachers on head-teachers' adoption of professional development programmes for quality assurance and internal efficiency of primary school teachers in Ekiti State. Similar results were equally found in related study by Wasserman and Migdal (2019) that investigated professional development: teachers' attitudes in online and traditional training course. The study found that there is relationship between staff development programme (conference, workshop, mentoring & job rotation) and teachers' attitude to work. The study however concluded that staff development programmes is an important variable that improves personal connection between the student and the teachers.

School Facility Management as a Strategy Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State.

Regarding school facility management as a strategy adopted by head-teacher for quality assurance in public primary schools in Anambra State, the results in Table 2 showed that the research participants consented that head-teachers of public primary schools adopt school facility management as a strategy for quality assurance in Anambra State. In Table 7, the results showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of head-teachers and teachers on adoption of school facility management as a strategy for quality assurance by head-teachers of public primary schools in Anambra State. From these results, it is obvious that head-teachers and teachers in Anambra State notwithstanding their position accepted that head-teachers adopt school facility management as a strategy for quality assurance. The logic behind this assertion is that research participants recognized that ensure adequacy of infrastructural facilities; check internet connection to classrooms; ensure adequacy and properly ventilated classrooms for effective teaching and learning; monitor school website for effective use; and check laboratory equipment and materials for adequacy and currency regularly to improve teaching and learning. The respondents also admitted that head-teachers check materials in the electronic libraries for adequacy and currency regularly; ensure use of updated textbooks and journals for currency and comprehensiveness; ensure adequate provisions for ICT utilization by teachers for instructional delivery; and check and ensure provision for regular power supply to offices, classrooms and laboratories for effective instructional delivery and effective implementation of the curriculum and programmes.

The above results agree with the findings of Alimi, Ehinola and Alabi (2012) who conducted a study on school types, facilities and academic performance of students in senior secondary schools in Ondo State, Nigeria. Their study revealed that school physical facilities such as recreational facilities, welfare facilities, and health facilities etcetera were identified as instrumental for teachers' effectiveness and productivity in the teaching and learning process and academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study further revealed a no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the influence of school facilities management on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ondo State. The findings also agree with the findings of a study in Anambra State by Okechukwu

(2022) on School plant and organizational climate as predictors of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. The study found that adequate provision and maintenance of physical infrastructure, large class size, health facilities, and recreational facilities had positive relationship with teachers' job performance level. This implies that education providers should ensure that physical facilities are adequately provided for teachers to improve in their productivity. Their study also found that school physical facilities significantly affect teachers' job performance.

Effective Instructional Supervision as a Strategy Adopted by Head-Teachers for Quality Assurance in Public Primary Schools in Anambra State.

The results in Table 3 indicated that the research subjects admitted that head-teachers of public primary schools adopt effective instructional supervision as a strategy for quality assurance in Anambra State. The results in Table 8 also indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean ratios of head-teachers and teachers on adoption of school effective instructional supervision as a strategy for quality assurance by head-teachers of public primary schools in Anambra State. One can see from the results that irrespective of rank, head-teachers and teachers in public primary schools in Anambra State indicated alike that head-teachers adopt effective instructional supervision as a strategy for quality assurance. As long as the respondents agreed that effective instructional supervision is a strategy for quality assurance, there is need for the head-teachers to make sure that teachers are adequately supervise to ensure that right instruction is delivered to learners. In any case, respondents' recognition that effective instructional supervision is a strategy for quality assurance does not necessarily imply that they are adequately provided. They may not be adequately provided but the ones provided are crucial to effective quality assurance in schools. Thus, the point behind effective instructional supervision as a strategy for quality assurance that the research participants acknowledged that head-teachers: constantly review contents taught in their schools; ensure that question papers are moderated before they are administered; ensure that appropriate methods are employed by teachers in their schools; constantly evaluate instructional materials used by teachers in their schools to ensure suitability; monitor students during practical exercises in their schools; and ensure high level of discipline during classroom instruction in their schools.

The findings on the head-teachers adoption of effective instructional supervision as a strategy quality assurance are supported by that of another study. Samoei (2014) research on instructional supervisory role of principals and its' influence on students' academic achievement in public secondary schools in Nandi North District Nandi County Kenya established that principals' orient new teaching staff supervises curriculum, timetabling and monitor students' academic progress; which are important factors that promote students' academic achievement. The study also found that instructional supervisory roles of the principals have great influence on students' academic achievement in Nandi North District, Nandi County Kenya. The findings of this study are also in congruence with the findings of Mbakwe (2022) in her work on principals' managerial skills as correlate of teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in Anambra State. The study findings showed that there is positive relationship between principals' supervision of instruction skills and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in

Anambra State. The study findings established that there is significant relationship between principals' supervision of instruction skills and teachers' task performance in public secondary schools in of Anambra State. One can infer that effective instructional supervision in schools will improve the quality assurance effectively.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that head-teachers and teachers in public primary schools in Anambra State adopted strategies of professional development programmes, school facilities management and effective instructional supervision for quality assurance by head-teachers of public primary schools. Thus, the study concluded that a proactive approach in these strategies can contribute to a positive learning environment, enhanced teacher effectiveness, and improved student outcomes, aligning with the objectives of quality assurance in primary education.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Governments should provide clear and comprehensive quality assurance for primary schools, outlining specific standards and expectations. They should also ensure adequate allocation of resources, including teaching materials, technology, and personnel, to support effective teaching and learning.
2. Head-teachers and teachers should undergo regular professional development training to stay informed about the latest educational practices and quality assurance methods.
3. Teachers should implement regular assessments to measure students' progress and identify areas for improvement. This helps in adjusting teaching strategies accordingly.

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